

How To Cluster

ESIP Collaboration Areas

How To Cluster in ESIP

ESIP Clusters, a type of Collaboration Area, are broadly defined as groups of Earth science professionals who collaborate on common challenges and opportunities. The [current list of ESIP Collaboration Areas can be found on our website](#). This document details how to start a new Cluster and get it operating smoothly.

There is no one-size-fits-all approach to leading an ESIP Cluster, and they are not intended to exist in perpetuity. They are proposed when a need or goal arises and are spun down when the goal has been achieved. In general, clusters have three phases in their life cycle:

1. [initiation phase](#)
2. [active phase](#)
3. [hiatus phase](#)

ESIP staff tailor their support to Clusters based on where the Cluster is in the life cycle. What follows is a series of instructions to aid Cluster leads in proposing, leading, and spinning down a Cluster broken down into sections referencing the three main phases. Contact staff@esipfed.org if you have any questions.

When to form a Cluster

Clusters allow members of the ESIP community to collaborate on an Earth Science challenge or opportunity that it has identified. Ideas for Clusters often originate from conversations at [ESIP meetings](#) but can arise at any time. Before jumping into the initiation phase, it's important to review the considerations and benefits available to a Cluster.

Considerations

- What does the Cluster hope to accomplish? What will be its goals?
- Are there enough members of the community interested in contributing to the activities of the Cluster?
- Is there an existing Cluster working on similar activities? Are there opportunities to consolidate efforts?
- Have you identified 1-2 individuals who would serve as a chair or co-chair? For a Cluster or other Cluster to function successfully, it must have a chair who takes the lead in

goal-setting, planning, advertising, facilitating, and documenting group activities. It is not a trivial time commitment. Roles and responsibilities are outlined in the [The ESIP Cluster Handbook](#).

Benefits and services available to a Cluster

- Recruitment of ESIP members to participate in Cluster activities
- Addition of monthly calls on the ESIP community calendar and shared via the weekly ESIP update
- Access to ESIP communication and collaboration spaces (e.g., Zoom, Google Drive, Google Group, Slack)
- Potential support from Community Fellows whose research aligns with your Cluster
- Support from ESIP staff

If you are still undecided about whether to start an ESIP Cluster, you can share your idea with the [ESIP General Mailing List](#) or with the ESIP #general Slack Channel to get feedback from the community.

Who can propose an ESIP Cluster?

Anyone who is employed by or is a member of an ESIP Partner Organization can propose an ESIP Cluster. If you are unsure if your organization is an ESIP Partner, you can find [a list on our website](#) or you can [email ESIP staff](#). If you are not a partner but have strong interest in forming a Cluster, please reach out to us. We want to support anyone interested in engaging in [the mission and vision of the organization and who shares our core values](#). In most cases, we can identify a community member affiliated with a partner organization who would be interested in supporting the effort.

The ESIP Cluster Life Cycle

Phase 1: Initiation Phase

Propose an ESIP Cluster

To propose an ESIP Cluster, you will need to [complete a form with the following information](#):

- Name of proposed Cluster
- Name of initial chairperson and co-chairperson
- Names, affiliations, and email addresses of committed members
- Preliminary description of Cluster and Cluster goals (*reference section [Set Cluster Goals](#)*)
 - What is the motivation for forming the Cluster? How will the Cluster know it is successful in terms of goals and outputs? What is the anticipated timeline for achieving your goals? If known, how does the Cluster fit in with or how will it

interact with others? How is this proposed work related to your day job? Is your employer supportive of your involvement in this effort?

All proposals will be reviewed by the Program Committee, chaired by the Board Vice President, in consultation with ESIP staff. The Vice President makes the final decision. Proposals will be reviewed considering the following criteria:

- Alignment of Cluster goals with the mission of ESIP
- Engagement of individuals affiliated with one or more partner organization (*reference section [Who can propose an ESIP cluster](#)*)
- Limited to no overlap with the goals and activities of existing Clusters
- Capacity of ESIP staff to support a new Cluster

Set up collaboration tools

Once your requested Cluster has been approved, you will be contacted and asked what ESIP collaborative tools you need. The basic collaborative support provided to Clusters by ESIP staff include: a dedicated mailing list, a Slack channel, access to Zoom for Cluster calls, an external Google drive, and a place on the ESIP website that briefly describes your Cluster and holds links to public documentation. Add-ons may include a GitHub Repo or access to ESIP's Amazon Web Services capabilities, depending on the needs of the Cluster.

Populate your webpage

One important step before advertising your Cluster to the broader community is to put some content on the ESIP website. This will be a landing page for people seeking information about what your Cluster does and to share any resources. This page should at least state in a paragraph or two what was in the preliminary description of the Cluster that you provided in your proposal (*reference section [Propose an ESIP Cluster](#)*). Think about what information a person would need to decide whether to get involved in your Cluster. Be sure to include how to join the mailing list, who to contact for questions, when your calls take place (once known), and any other relevant information. You should also include a link to your running notes document and a link to your preliminary Cluster Plan (*reference section [Setting Cluster Goals](#)*). You should aim to update your webpage periodically, but at least annually during the annual check-in with ESIP staff. Updates for your Cluster webpage should be coordinated with ESIP staff by contacting community@esipfed.org.

Schedule and advertise your first meeting

Once your collaborative tools are in place and you are pleased with your webpage, it is up to you to choose a time for the first meeting for your Cluster. You may wish to have a brainstorming session with your co-chair(s) or with a few interested community members to develop a strategy for the early phase of the Cluster prior to inviting others in. Or you may wish to wait to find out who turns up and is likely to be involved in the Cluster before developing a further strategy. If your initial meeting is open to all, please [email details to the Communications Director](#) at least 10 days in advance so that the call can be advertised more broadly within the ESIP community.

Phase 2: Active Phase

The active phase is defined as all activities happening during and after the first meeting of the Cluster. There is no one-size-fits-all approach to running a Cluster, and ESIP staff will not rigidly prescribe how you work. You likely formed a Cluster around an Earth science challenge or opportunity, so you should find the structure and format that best helps you take steps toward addressing that challenge or opportunity. Additional details about running your Cluster are included in [The ESIP Cluster Handbook](#).

Set Cluster goals

Although goal setting is included in the active phase, it should be something that started even prior to proposing the Cluster. The reason for its inclusion in the active phase is that goals should not be solidified until you know who will take part in the Cluster and what they hope to get out of participation. Your Cluster should set **concrete and measurable goals** to assess progress. You may also want to consider breaking larger goals down into smaller sub-goals, so you have **smaller, but more frequent, milestones** to celebrate. Lay these goals out clearly in a **succinct Cluster plan** ([a template is available for you to copy](#)). The plan should be shared with all Cluster members and linked on the Cluster's webpage, as well as reviewed and updated each year alongside ESIP staff during a scheduled annual check-in. The most ideal times to review and update your Cluster plan may be just after the Winter or Summer ESIP Meetings because it is likely that activities from the meeting may help you refine future directions. When a new Cluster is started, the chairs may draft an initial plan that is then refined through subsequent Cluster events. Some examples of concrete goals are listed below, but we also recommend referencing this resource to consider equity and inclusion in your goal setting ([SMARTIE Goals worksheet](#)).

Example goals

- To raise awareness of new research in an Earth Science field
 - Possible activity: monthly webinar series, shared via ESIP's communication channels, featuring a diversity of authors on new publications
- To synthesize best practices in archiving an Earth Science dataset
 - Possible activity: monthly co-working calls to identify relevant publications / resources to synthesize into a white paper
- To curate available datasets relevant to an Earth Science field
 - Possible activity: monthly co-working calls to develop a curation method to adopt and then adding datasets based on that methodology

Elect Cluster chairs and co-chairs

Individuals who propose an ESIP Cluster typically start off in the position of Cluster chair and co-chair(s). A Cluster should consider electing a new chair and 1-2 co-chairs every 1-2 years to prevent burnout. Elections could take place by a simple majority vote on a Cluster call or could be more formally run through an electronic platform with assistance from ESIP staff. If you do hold an election, at a minimum, a notification should be sent to the Cluster mailing list at least two weeks in advance of the election. Final results should be shared via the mailing list, and

ESIP staff should be notified of any leadership changes. When considering whether to run for chair of a Cluster, individuals should take into account the roles and responsibilities described in [The ESIP Cluster Handbook](#). An individual who has rotated off as Chair of a Cluster can still remain very active in the group.

Set up your Cluster call

For most Clusters, monthly hour-long meetings are the primary event and communication pathway for Cluster progress. Your Cluster may choose to meet more or less frequently (but *reference section [Hiatus Phase](#)*). Often, it works well to set the call on a recurring schedule (e.g., on the first Tuesday of the month at 1 pm ET), so that meetings are predictable. When identifying a regular time slot, please try to avoid times that conflict with other ESIP Cluster calls, as shown on the [ESIP Community Calendar](#). Once an ideal time slot has been identified, [notify ESIP staff](#), so that the Zoom link can be set up and details can be shared on the ESIP Community Calendar.

Review The ESIP Cluster Handbook

Once your Cluster is fully up and running, [The ESIP Cluster Handbook](#) will contain all the information you need to guide your Cluster. This includes: roles and responsibilities of chairs, staff, and Community Fellows; links to communication and collaboration spaces; step-by-step guides; links to relevant resources; and FAQs. All leaders in your new Cluster should become familiar with its content as it will be your go-to resource during the Cluster's active phase.

Annual Check-Ins

Clusters in the active phase will be asked to meet once a year with a member of ESIP staff. This annual check-in, which can be done during a regular Cluster call, will be a time to reflect on accomplishments of the past year and to identify goals for the coming year. Accomplishments and annual goals will continue to be captured in the [Cluster Plan](#). These check-ins will also be a time to determine if a Cluster should consider entering [hiatus phase](#).

Special Project Funding

The ESIP Finance Committee has a small amount of funding available for ESIP Clusters to request funds for special projects. These special projects must support [ESIP's mission and vision](#) and align with ESIP's current strategic goals. The special project mechanism is intended to provide a flexible funding vehicle to quickly support high impact activities of interest to the ESIP community.

Phase 3: Hiatus Phase

ESIP Clusters that have achieved their goals or are in a period of low activity (defined as 4 consecutive months with no virtual meetings or other activities) should consider entering hiatus phase. Hiatus phase is not a sign of failure - it can, in fact, be a sign of success. ESIP Clusters are not meant to exist indefinitely, but to exist for a time to work towards established goals and then enter into hiatus phase. An important step prior to hiatus phase is to ensure that the history

of the Cluster, including its activities and any outputs produced, is preserved. The following information should be added to your [Cluster Plan](#):

- Year Initiated
- Month / Year entering Hiatus Phase
- Reason for entering Hiatus Phase
- Cluster goals achieved
- Outgoing Cluster leaders, including who to contact with questions
- Key milestones, including presentations and activities within and outside of ESIP
- List of outputs, including where to access each

Once this information has been completed, the plan should be [submitted to ESIP staff](#) so they can make appropriate updates to the webpage and other communication channels.

Returning to active phase

If a follow-on goal or activity is identified, the Cluster can return to [active phase](#) again at any point in the future. Please [contact ESIP staff](#) to inform them of your interest, and we will work with you to identify next steps. Depending on how long the Cluster has been inactive, it may require returning to the initiation phase to

Acknowledgements

ESIP is generously supported by NASA, NOAA, and the USGS. We would like to thank previous ESIP staff and community members who shepherded ESIP Clusters and developed some of the processes outlined here.